

ANALYSIS OF AUTOMATIC GAS PRESSURE REGULATION IN GAS SUPPLY SYSTEMS

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***Abstract.** The article analyzes some of the shortcomings that arise during the operation of gas networks and measures to eliminate these shortcomings. At present, saving natural gas and automatic regulation of gas pressure are among the main issues*

***Keywords:** gas networks, gas pipelines, energy efficiency, gas consumers, reliability, equipment*

Introduction. In the process of fuel extraction their value increases as they are extracted deeper and deeper. Therefore, it is natural that the need to save fuel costs becomes the main problem of the development of the national economy of our country. The growing cost of fuel energy throughout the world shows that fuel is essentially a limited resource. Therefore, it is the duty of every conscious person to save fuel energy in our country [1-4].

Gas distribution networks are the energy arteries of populated areas; therefore, any technical and structural problems are of great importance.

Gas supply and gasification enterprises and organizations face enormous challenges in ensuring uninterrupted and reliable gas supply.

Experimental studies. Gas supply systems operate around the clock with variable modes depending on the nature of gas consumption. The greatest unevenness of gas consumption is inherent in small household consumers, however, fluctuations in gas consumption for household needs have a certain pattern.

Hourly fluctuations confirm the lack of complete repeatability of daily schedules even on ordinary days of the same week and a significant change in the nature of uneven gas consumption by season, on pre-holiday days. Usually, the daily consumption schedule is characterized by morning and evening peaks, and at night gas consumption decreases several dozen times. Uneven gas consumption is caused by a large number of factors, the main ones being: climatic conditions, the way of life of the population of a particular area, the working hours of enterprises and institutions, the state of the housing stock, the degree of gasification of different categories of consumers. Uneven gas consumption determines the pressure modes in urban gas networks. Continuous periodic deviations in gas consumption by hours of the day from the average daily value have a major impact on the operating modes of gas equipment and automatic control devices.

The nature of the average daily gas consumption of municipal and household consumers has been sufficiently studied and can be considered as a continuous periodic function with a period of 24 hours (1 day) in the annual context (Fig. 1.0), represented by a Fourier series. The sum of the Fourier series taking into account the numerical values of the coefficient for the average daily gas consumption will have the form:

$$Q(t) = 4.2 + (-1.2)\cos\frac{2\pi t}{24} + (0.05)\cos2\frac{2\pi t}{24} + (0.08)\cos3\frac{2\pi t}{24} + (-0.08)\cos4\frac{2\pi t}{24} + 0.17\cos5\frac{2\pi t}{24} + (-2.02)\sin\frac{2\pi t}{24} + (-1.86)\sin2\frac{2\pi t}{24} + (-0.04)\sin3\frac{2\pi t}{24} + 0.09\sin4\frac{2\pi t}{24} + 0.04\sin\frac{2\pi t}{24} \quad (1.0)$$

Fig. 1 – Graph of average daily gas consumption with household load.

All harmonic components of the Fourier series of the expression have a very definite effect on the main controlled pressure parameter, since these harmonic components approximate the average daily gas consumption very well. Higher harmonic components are intensively suppressed by the object and do not have a significant effect on the fluctuations of the controlled pressure. Expression (1.0) can be used to determine the upper limit of the frequency, the effect of which must be taken into account. This frequency corresponds to $\omega = 0.022 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The lower limit of the frequency can be taken equal to zero, as the limit, which corresponds to the stepwise effect of the disturbance on the system ($t = \infty$), i.e. It is possible to limit ourselves to the spectrum of frequencies acting on the system in the range $\omega = 0 \div 0.022 \text{ min}^{-1}$.

As is known, the most effective solution to the issues of pressure control in gas supply systems can be achieved by analyzing the main controlled process - the unsteady movement of gas in distribution gas pipelines. Since urban gas supply systems consist of several stages of gas distribution, the unsteady movement of gas in low-pressure distribution gas pipelines will be caused by hourly unevenness of gas consumption and the presence of variable pressures at the inlet of the gas distribution pipeline. This is explained by the fact that low-pressure gas pipelines supply mainly mass household consumers [5-13].

The main requirement for the gas supply system and at the same time one of the most difficult aspects to implement is maintaining the gas pressure of equipment and devices using gas at a certain permissible value with arbitrary changes in the flow rate in the network, in a wide range. When the gas pressure increases compared to the nominal, the operating modes of devices and apparatus using gas are disrupted, and when the pressure decreases, their efficiency and productivity decrease.

The cost of designing, constructing and operating gas supply systems depends mainly on the population, the density and number of storeys of buildings, the structure of the fuel and

energy balance, the number of gas consumers and energy capacities, as well as their geographic location.

As is known, gas is supplied to gasified cities, towns or industrial facilities from main gas pipelines through gas distribution stations (GDS). GDS are the final objects of the main gas pipeline and perform the following tasks: gas purification from mechanical impurities; reducing the gas pressure to a given value and automatically maintaining this value; heating of gas before pressure reduction, preventing the release of solid crystal hydrates and freezing of pipelines and fittings; protection of pipelines from unacceptable increases in pressure; gas odorization; accounting of the flow rate and quantity of passing gas.

From the GDS, gas is transported through a medium or high pressure network to gas regulation stations (GRS), located in heated detached buildings, where the gas pressure is reduced and it is fed into distribution gas pipelines of different pressure categories. The most branched and, therefore, long and expensive are low-pressure distribution gas pipelines, which supply the mass consumer (residential buildings, small industrial and municipal household consumers). Gas pipelines are laid mainly underground, their diameters usually vary from 50 to 400 mm. This requires the installation of electrochemical protection, insulation of pipelines, gas wells, control and measuring points; therefore, gas pipelines are characterized by significant metal consumption.

The main requirement for the gas supply system and at the same time the most difficult to fulfill is maintaining the gas pressure in gas-using equipment and devices at a given optimal value with arbitrary changes in flow in the network over a wide range. When the gas pressure increases against the nominal value, the operating modes of gas-using devices and installations are disrupted, and when the pressure decreases, their efficiency and productivity decrease[2-9].

The difficulty of maintaining the nominal gas pressure with the required accuracy for consumers is due to the fact that the service radius of a separate gas distribution point often reaches 900-1500 m, which leads to a significant drop in gas pressure depending on the distance of consumers from the gas distribution point.

Fig. 2 - Diagram of gas network layout.

Reliable and stable operation of gas supply systems is impossible without reliable operation of control and safety shut-off valves and equipment. The first and main condition for stable and safe operation of the gas supply system is to ensure constant pressure; the second condition is protection against a possible increase or decrease in gas pressure at a controlled point of the gas pipeline or in front of a gas-using installation, unit or consumer device in excess of permissible values.

In accordance with these conditions, the GRP, GRU or combined pressure regulator includes the following elements:

- 1) pressure regulator, reducing gas pressure and automatically maintaining it at a given level regardless of changes in flow rate and input pressure;
- 2) safety shut-off valve, stopping gas supply in case of emergency increase or decrease in gas pressure after the regulator 50 above the set limits;
- 3) safety relief device, preventing an increase in gas pressure after the regulator to exclude false operation of the safety shut-off valve. This is usually observed in the system during transient modes or no gas consumption and during gas leaks through a closed pressure regulator valve;
- 4) filter for cleaning gas from mechanical impurities.

Currently, the economic factor is becoming increasingly important. Thus, the use of polyethylene pipes in the construction of gas pipelines reduces the costs of construction work and operation.

When designing or reconstructing gas supply systems, the choice of gas pressure in gas pipelines is of great importance. The higher it is accepted, the smaller the diameter of the gas pipeline is required. Often in populated areas there is a need to install regulating devices directly at gas consumers [2-5, 7-14].

When reconstructing worn-out gas pipelines, the most effective, from the point of view of the cost of construction work and subsequent operation, is to pull polyethylene pipes through them, while the cross-section of the gas pipeline is reduced and there is a need to increase the pressure in it, and therefore the need to install house regulators or cabinet regulating points.

Conclusions. It can be said that the closer the control device is to the gas consumer, the more accurately the pressure in front of it is maintained, that is, the gas equipment operates with good efficiency in the passport mode and less harmful emissions into the atmosphere.

The correct choice of the number, type and location of control devices determines not only the technical and economic indicators, but also the reliability of the entire gas distribution system.

With the introduction of a regional automated gas distribution control system, the level of technical and economic indicators will be even higher.

REFERENCES

1. *Ionin A. A.* Gas supply. - M.: Stroyizdat, 1989. - 438 p.
2. *Bayasanov D. B., Gurvich G. M.* Automatic regulation and control in urban gas networks - M.: Stroyizdat, 1970. - 192 p.
3. *Jila V. A.* Gas supply. Textbook for universities. M.: ASV Publishing House, 2014. -368 p.
4. *K. G. Kyazimov, V. E. Gusev.* Device and operation of gas facilities: Textbook - M.: Academy, 2013. - 432 p.
5. *Sedak V. S., Suponev V. N., Slatova O. N.* Ways to improve the safety of gas supply systems. Labor protection. Scientific and production journal – 2009. – 10, 45-47 p.

6. *Karyakin E.A, Udovenko V.E, et al.* Industrial gas equipment: Reference book – Saratov, 2002. – 623 p.
7. *Aymatov R.R.* Combustion of gaseous fuel in industrial furnaces in the production of building materials in the republic of Uzbekistan. BST: bulletin of construction equipment. Moscow, 2019.
8. *Aymatov R.R.* Mathematical modeling of the combustion process. International scientific and practical conference on the topic "Problems and solutions for the implementation of innovative technologies in the field of engineering communications". Samarkand, 2020.
9. *Aymatov R.R.* Investigation of the efficiency of using gaseous fuel in the production of lime in rotary kilns. International journal of progressive sciences and technologies. Vol. 27 no. 1. [http: ijpsat.ijs'ht-journals.org](http://ijpsat.ijs'ht-journals.org)
10. *R.R. Aymatov, B.Mamatov, Q. Barotov.* Development of an economic and mathematical model for the optimal development of gas supply systems. European journal of life safety and stability (2660-9630). Published 2021-12-29.
11. *Aymatov R.R, Omonkulov O.X, Radjabov U.* Environmental impact of fuel energy complex networks and measures to reduce it. Publisher: “World of conferences” published 2022-12-22.
12. *A. Khalmanov, R. Aymatov, B. Turdikulov.* Optimization of the ventilation system and gas supply in the process of burning. ISJ theoretical & applied science. Vol.9 no. 101. Published 2021.
13. *Aymatov R.R, Rajabov U.* Study of the working process of heating, heat-generating gas equipment used in housing and communal services - scientific and technical journal "problems of architecture and construction". Issue 4 (part 2), 2022.
14. IGU. proceedings of the 21st world gas conference, june 6-9, 2000.